

Reproductive Ecology of *Morenia ocellata* (Dume'ril and Bibron, 1835) and *Lissemys scutata* (Peters, 1868) from the Lake of Zena Man Aung Pagoda Compound, Thaketa Township, Yangon Region

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Abstract

The reproductive ecology of the Myanmar endemic species *Morenia ocellata* (Dume'ril and Bibron, 1835) and *Lissemys scutata* (Peters, 1868) at the lake of Zena Man Aung Pagoda compound, Thaketa Township, Yangon Region were investigated from December 2013 to July 2014. The egg laying period of both turtle species was found during the cool season between December 2013 and January 2014 at the maximum atmospheric temperature between 30°C and 38.2°C. A total of 27 nests of *Morenia ocellata* and 8 nests of *Lissemys scutata* were recorded in this study. The clutch sizes of both species were large: 1-21 eggs (mean 6.59 ± 4.63) in *Morenia ocellata* and 2-20 eggs (mean 7.38 ± 5.98) in *Lissemys scutata*. The nesting sites of *Morenia ocellata* were observed in the loam soil (74%) and between shaded stones (26%). The nesting sites of *Lissemys scutata* were observed in the loam soil (50%), on un-shaded soil (37.5%) and under shaded plants (12.5%). The nests of *Morenia ocellata* (67%) were observed away from the edge of water surface between 150 cm and above. The nests of *Lissemys scutata* (87.5%) were observed near the edge of water surface between 50 cm and 140 cm. The depth of the nests of *Morenia ocellata* was deeper (5 cm- 7 cm) than the *Lissemys scutata* (2 cm -7 cm). The eggs of *Morenia ocellata* were observed as egg shaped and whitish in color while *Lissemys scutata* were spherical and also whitish. Hatching time was found between May 2014 to June 2014 in *Morenia ocellata* species and June 2014 to July 2014 in *Lissemys scutata*. The incubation period of *Morenia ocellata* was shorter (160-190 days) than the *Morenia ocellata* (190-210 days). Reproductive performance of the turtle species is greatly importance for the next generation as a conservation aspect. Most of the turtle species are now under threatened level as per International Union for the Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources (IUCN).

Introduction

Turtles are ancient animals that evolved over 200 million years ago, well before the age of Dinosaurs. They belong to the Class Reptilia, Phylum Chordata. They have the distinguishing characteristics of a body covering shell. These shelled reptiles constitute the order Testudines (Ernst and Barbour, 1989).

Turtles served as a food supply for early humans, and continue to benefit us by destroying crop pests, dispersing seeds of forest trees, and cleaning our rivers by grazing on algae and aquatic weeds (Kalyar *et al.*, 2012).

The diversity of turtles and tortoises in the world consists of 328 species. Of the 328 total species, 156 are threatened and 90 are critically endangered, or vulnerable (Rhodin, 2010). A total of 32 marine and non-marine chelonian species are recorded from Myanmar, seven of them are endemic species (Win Maung and Win Ko Ko, 2002).

Turtle reproduce sexually and fertilization is internal. Male turtles usually have a larger tail, thicker and wider than that of the female. In the latter sex, the plastron is flat, whereas in many species the males have to some degree, a plastral concavity (Bonin, 2006).

All female turtles lay eggs; these are spherical or elliptical, usually white, and with a shell that varies from soft and leathery to calcareous and brittle. Some freshwater turtles may lay at least three times during a season, although others almost certainly lay all their eggs for the season at one time (Carr, 1952). The number of eggs laid in a clutch also varies between

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species – from 1 single egg in the case of *Malacochersus tornieri* (the pan cake tortoise) to 20 or more eggs per clutch in *Geochelone pardalis* (High Field, 1996).

The eggs of turtles are laid in holes in soil, sand, or decaying vegetation such as leaf mold or rotten wood. The nests are dug by the female. More or less flask-shaped hole of a depth is determined by the length of the stretched hind leg. The nesting process is attended by the wetting of the soil by cloacal bladder water of female turtle which softens it and makes digging easier (Carr, 1952).

Incubation periods normally range between two and three months, but are so strongly affected by humidity and temperature (Carr, 1952). In many cases, hatching in the wild coincides with the first rainfall following the hot summer incubation period. As the ground becomes saturated by water, its permeability to oxygen is drastically reduced. This causes a corresponding rise in CO₂ levels within the buried eggs which in turn triggers emergence (High Field, 1996).

In some turtle species, temperature determines whether an egg develops into a male or a female: a higher temperature causes a female, a lower temperature causes a male (Janzen, 1994).

The huge demand for turtles as food, ingredients of traditional Chinese medicine, and pets has left many species tottering on the brink of extinction. Without conservation action, most of the 26 species of turtles in Myanmar are likely to go extinct in the very near future. With the respect of above mentioned the present study was conducted.

Aims and Objectives

- To record the egg laying period and nesting sites of the study species
- To examine the characters and microclimate of the nests
- To observe the clutch size of turtle species and the character of eggs
- To record the hatching time and incubation period of turtle species

Materials and Methods

Study area and study site

Turtle pond at Zena Man Aung pagoda was selected as the study site. This pagoda was situated in Thaketa Township (16°48' N and 096°12' E) in Yangon Region. Turtle pond was of concrete type with the dimension of (360 cm × 350 cm × 150 cm). The water level was 140 cm. There were some breeding grounds between the fence and the edge of water with clay, gravel stone and loam soil to build the nesting sites for the gravid female turtles.

Study period

Three consecutive days per week were spent at the study site during 12 am to 5 pm to observe and record the breeding turtles. The study period lasted from December, 2013 to July, 2014.

Observation on nests

The number of nests and the number of eggs per nest were counted and recorded in the field data form. The structure of nests and the distance of nest sites to the water edge were measured with a measuring tape and a ruler. Nest sites were marked and numbered by bamboo sticks with labels. The nest holes were dug up manually in order to observe and record the clutch size per nest.

Observation on eggs

Morphometric measurements of eggs were done with a measuring tape and a digital scale and recorded in the field data form. Clutch size was calculated by enumerating the eggs laid in nests. The incubation period was calculated from the day of recording the eggs underneath the soil.

Recording the weather parameters

Recording the ambient atmospheric parameters near the pond was done by a thermo-hygrometer. The temperature inside the nests was measured with a thermometer. Artificial nest-like holes were dug by using sharp stick and the ground temperature was recorded on every study day.

Results

A total of 27 nests of Myanmar endemic species: *Morenia ocellata* and 8 nests of *Lissemys scutata* were recorded in this study (Table 1). The egg laying period of *Morenia ocellata* was found between 2nd week of December and 2nd week of January while *Lissemys scutata* was between 3rd week of December and 2nd week of January (Table 1).

The nesting sites of *Morenia ocellata* were in the loam soil (74 %) and between shaded stones (26 %). The nesting sites of *Lissemys scutata* were in the loam soil (50 %), on un-shaded soil (37.5 %) and under shaded plants (12.5%) (Plate 3) (Table 2). Nests of *Morenia ocellata* were observed at 100-200 cm (mean 155.37 ± 33.33 cm) away from the edge of the water (Table 2). Nests of *Lissemys scutata* were also observed at 50-160 cm (mean 90.63 ± 41.27 cm) away from the edge of the water (Table 3).

The depth of the nests of *Morenia ocellata* varied from 5 to 7 cm (mean 6.25 ± 0.82 cm) and the diameter varied between 5 to 18cm (mean 11.38 ± 4.93 cm). The depth of the nests of *Lissemys scutata* varied from 2 to 4 cm (mean 2.75 ± 0.82 cm) and the diameter varied between 7 to 18 cm (mean 13.35 ± 2.91 cm) (Table 4 and 5). The clutch size of *Morenia ocellata* was 1-21 eggs (mean 6.59 ± 4.63) and the clutch size of *Lissemys scutata* was 2-20 eggs (mean 7.38 ± 5.98) (Table 6).

The shape of eggs of *Morenia ocellata* was egg shaped. The shape of eggs of *Lissemys scutata* was spherical like tennis ball. The shell of both turtle species was delicate, fine and brittle. The fresh eggs of both turtle species were usually whitish in colour, sometimes brownish (Plate 3).

The weight of individual eggs of *Morenia ocellata* from a clutch varied from 14.57 to 20.02 g (mean 18.02 ± 2.02 g; n=7). The girth of individual eggs of *Morenia ocellata* from a clutch varied from 8.0 to 8.5 cm (mean 8.21 ± 0.25 cm; n=7). The weight of individual eggs of *Lissemys scutata* from a clutch varied from 13.58 to 15.56 g (mean 14.87 ± 0.68 g; n=7). The girth of individual eggs of *Lissemys scutata* from a clutch varied from 9.0 to 9.9 cm (mean 9.43 ± 0.29 cm; n=7) (Table 7).

The mean weekly temperature in the ground at the time of nesting period varied from 30 to 34°C, humidity in the air from 35 to 49 % and temperature in the air from 31.5 to 36.4°C (Table 1). The mean weekly temperature in the ground at the time of hatching period varied from 30 to 35°C, humidity in the air from 40 to 90% and temperature in air from 30 to 35°C (Table 8).

Hatching time was found between 3rd week of May and last week of June in *Morenia ocellata* and last week of June and last week of July in *Lissemys scutata*. The incubation period

varied between 160 and 190 days in *Morenia ocellata* species and 190 and 210 days in *Lissemys scutata* (Table 8).

Eggs from 20 nests of *Morenia ocellata* were disappeared, 3 nests were spoiled and 4 nests were hatched out. The eggs from 2 nests of *Lissemys scutata* were disappeared, 3 nests were spoiled and 3 nests were hatched out. Hatching success was not calculated (Table 9).

Table 1. Numbers of Nests of Turtles and the Weather Parameters recorded in the Study Period

Study Period	Turtle Species		Mean Max. Temp. of Air (°C)	Mean Max. Relative Humidity of Air (%)	Mean Temp. in the Ground (°C)
	<i>Morenia ocellata</i>	<i>Lissemys scutata</i>			
Week 1	-	-	36.2	45	30
December 1 st week	-	-	(34.2-38.2)	(43-47)	(30-30)
Week 2	6	-	36.4	49	30
December 2 nd week	6	-	(35.8-37)	(47-51)	(30-30)
Week 3	6	2	34.1	41.5	30
December 3 rd week	6	2	(32-36.8)	(40-43)	(30-30)
Week 4	9	2	31.5	44	30.5
December last week	9	2	(31-32)	(43-45)	(30-31)
Week 5	2	1	34	48	33
January 1 st week	2	1	(34-34)	(44-52)	(33-33)
Week 6	2	2	33.75	37	33.5
January 2 nd week	2	2	(33-33.5)	(35-39)	(33-34)
Week 7	2	1	33	35	34
January 3 rd week	2	1	(33-33)	(33-37)	(33-34)
Total	27	8			

Table 2. Recorded Nesting Sites of Turtle Species in the Study Site

Nesting Sites	Turtle Nest Number (%)	
	<i>M. ocellata</i>	<i>L. scutata</i>
In the loam soil	74	50
Between shaded stones	26	-
Under shaded plants	-	12.5
On un-shaded soil	-	37.5
Total	100	100

Table 3. Recorded Nest Distance of Turtle Species from the Edge of Water

Distance of Nests from the Edge of Water (cm)	Turtle Nest Number (%)	
	<i>M. ocellata</i>	<i>L. scutata</i>
50-99	-	62.5
100-125	29.63	12.5
126-150	18.52	12.5
151-175	14.81	12.5
176-200	37.04	-
Total	100	100

Table 4. Recorded Nests Depth of Turtle Species in the Study Site

Nest Depth (cm)	Turtle nest number (%)	
	<i>M. ocellata</i>	<i>L. scutata</i>
Between stones/ On moist soil	25.93	50
2-4	-	50
5	48.15	-
6	14.81	-
7	11.11	-
Total	100	100

Table 5. Recorded Nests Diameter of Turtle Species in the Study Site

Nest diameter (cm)	Turtle nest number (%)	
	<i>M. ocellata</i>	<i>L. scutata</i>
Between stones/ On moist soil	25.93	50
5	22.22	-
6-10	3.7	12.5
11-15	33.33	25.0
16- 18	14.81	12.5
Total	100	100

Table 6. Recorded Clutch Sizes of Turtle Species in the Study Site

Number of Eggs Laid per Clutch	Turtle Nest Number	
	<i>M. ocellata</i>	<i>L. scutata</i>
1-5	12	4
6-10	9	2
11-15	5	1
16-20	-	1
21	1	-
Total	27	8

Table 7. Morphometric Parameters of Eggs of *M. ocellata* and *L. scutata* from Each Clutch (n=7)

Egg No.	<i>M. ocellata</i>		<i>L. scutata</i>	
	L (cm)	G (cm) W (g)	G (cm)	W (g)
1.	11	8 19.13	9.5	15.34
2.	10.5	8 16.34	9.4	14.58
3.	10	8 14.57	9.6	14.96
4.	10.6	8 16.49	9.2	14.11
5.	11.5	8.5 20.02	9.9	15.43
6.	11	8.5 19.87	9.0	13.58
7.	11	8.5 19.71	9.5	15.56
Range	10.0-11.5	8.0 - 8.5 14.5 - 20.02	9.0 - 9.9	13.58 - 15.56
Mean ± SD	10.79 ± 0.45	8.21± 0.25 18.02 ± 2.02	9.43 ± 0.29	14.87 ± 0.68

L = Length; G = Girth; W = Weight

Table 8. Incubation Period of Turtle Species and Recorded Parameters

Turtle species	Incubation period from a clutch (days)	Mean			Hatching period
		Max. Temp. of Air (°C)	Max. RH of Air (%)	Temp. in ground (°C)	
<i>M. ocellata</i>	160-173	32.5-35	40-60	34-36	May 3 rd week to June 1 st week
<i>M. ocellata</i>	165-179	32-35	45-64	34-36	May last week to June 2 nd week
<i>M. ocellata</i>	167-190	31-32.5	64-74	34-36	June 2 nd week to June last week
<i>M. ocellata</i>	160-169	31-32	73-74	34-35	June 3 rd week to June last week
<i>L. scutata</i>	190-210	31-34	54-74	30-34	June last week to July 3 rd week
<i>L. scutata</i>	190-205	30-31	68-80	30-32	June last week to July 2 nd week
<i>L. scutata</i>	193-207	30-34	54-90	30-30	July 3 rd week to July last week

Max = Maximum; Temp. = Temperature; RH = Relative Humidity

Table 9. Hatching and Non-Hatching Nests due to Human Impacts

Fate of nests	Turtle Nest Number			
	<i>M. ocellata</i>	%	<i>L. scutata</i>	%
Damage nests due to human impact	20	74.01	2	25.00
Spoiled nests	3	11.11	3	37.50
Hatching nests	4	14.81	3	37.50
Total	27	100	8	100

Discussion and Conclusion

During the study period, 27 nests of Myanmar Eyed turtle *Morenia ocellata* and 8 nests of Myanmar Flap Shell turtle *Lissemys scutata* were recorded in the study pond. The nests of *Morenia ocellata* were more abundant than the nests of *Lissemys scutata* in the study pond. This may be due to the population size of *Morenia ocellata* which were higher than those of *Lissemys scutata*. The highest number of nests of both species was found in the last week of December, 2013 between the maximum temperature 31°C and 32°C at the air and 30°C and 31°C at a ground surface temperature. The range of atmospheric temperature might be optimum for the gravid female turtles to build the nests.

Win Maung and Win Ko Ko (2002) mentioned that the nesting season of *Morenia ocellata* is from September to April and *Lissemys scutata* is from September to October. The present study showed that the nesting season of both turtle species was from December to January.

In the present study, both the female turtle species chose the loam soil as the most preferable nesting site. The present investigation supported the statement of Hossian *et al.* (2010) that the nesting sites of *Lissemys punctata* were in the loam soil (76%) and less in sandy (24%) soil. Win Maung and Win Ko Ko (2002) reported that nesting sites of *Morenia ocellata* is wet muddy and *Lissemys scutata* is soil.

According to Hossian *et al.* (2010) the depth of the nests of *Lissemys punctata* varied from 8.8 cm to 10.6 cm (mean 9.8±0.6 cm) and the diameter varied between 9.9 cm and 12.0 cm (mean 11.0±0.6 cm) in nature. Win Maung and Win Ko Ko (2002) reported that the nest depth of both turtle species is shallow. The present study showed that 50% of the depth of *Lissemys scutata* nests was 2 cm to 4 cm and 50% of the nests were made at random on the soil in captive situation at the study site. The depth of the nests of *Morenia ocellata* (48.15%) was 5 cm. The present findings suggested that suitable soil (loam soil) will be needed at the turtle pond for the gravid female turtles to lay eggs.

The clutch size of *Morenia ocellata* is 5-8 eggs and *Lissemys scutata* is 3-8 eggs (Win Maung and Win Ko Ko, 2002). The present study showed that the clutch size of *Morenia ocellata* varied from 1 to 21 eggs (mean 6.59±4.63) and *Lissemys scutata* varied from 2 to 20 eggs (mean 7.38±5.98). It was observed that the greater the clutch size of both turtle species the higher the diameter and the greater the depth of the nests. The clutch sizes of both turtle species were large so that the population size of these species may be kept in future.

During the present study it was noted that the body shape of turtles and the egg shapes were related in both turtle species. The body shape and the egg shape of *Morenia ocellata* was elongated while the body and the egg was spherical shape in *Lissemys scutata*. Egg dimension was also varied in each clutch. It was found that the dimension of the eggs was also increased when weight of eggs increased.

Hossain *et al.*, (2010) stated that the incubation period of *Lissemys punctata* may vary 60-260 days depending on the ground surface temperature. The incubation period was 50 days with 30°C in an average; about 9 months at 32.2°C in the nest; 60-230 days for in north India. Hatching time was from April to July and the highest was in May. The present study showed that the incubation period of *Lissemys scutata* varied from 190 to 210 days at the ground surface temperature between 30°C and 34°C. The hatching time of this species was found between June last week to July last week.

During the study period, the eggs from 20 nests of *Morenia ocellata* and 2 nests of *Lissemys scutata* were disappeared from the pond of Zena Man Aung Pagoda, it may be due to human impacts, taken by the man. The adult turtles and their eggs may also be exploited in nature by man. Thus, the conservation action plan would be needed in the breeding sites of turtles in nature and turtle ponds from all pagoda campus. The second time of egg laying by *Lissemys scutata* was observed in July 2014. It can be concluded that this species breed at least twice a year.

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A. Turtle pond

B. Breeding ground at the turtle pond

C. Making a nest by female *Morenia ocellata*

D. Female *Lissemys scutata* found in a nest

E. Shell pieces of *Morenia ocellata* found at the study site

F. Shell pieces of *Lissemys scutata* found at the study site

Plate 1. The study site

A. *Morenia ocellata* (Dorsal view)

B. *Lissemys scutata* (Dorsal view)

(Male is on the left and female is on the right.)

C. *Morenia ocellata* (Juvenile) (Dorsal view)

D. *Lissemys scutata* (Juvenile) (Dorsal view)

Plate 2. Adults and Juveniles of *Morenia ocellata* and *Lissemys scutata*

A. Nest of *M. ocellata* (In the loam soil)

B. Nest of *M. ocellata* (Between shaded stone)

C. Nest of *L. scutata* (In the loam soil)

D. Nest of *L. scutata* (On un-shaded moist soil)

Plate 3. Nesting sites of *Morenia ocellata* and *Lissemys scutata*